

Intent-Driven Deployment and Live Migration Using LLM

João Fonseca*, Gerezihir Adhane*, Konstantinos Togias[†], Jhofre Ojeda*, Swastika Roy*, Golshan Famitafreshi*, Kostas Ramantas*, John Vardakas*[§] and Christos Verikoukis^{†‡}

*Iquadrat Informática, S.L., Barcelona Spain

Email: {j.fonseca,g.adhane,j.ojeda,s.roy,g.famitafreshi,kramantas,jvardakas}@iquadrat.com

^{†‡}Industrial Systems Institute/Athena Research Center

Email: ktogias@isi.gr

[‡]University of Patras, Greece

Email: cveri@ceid.upatras.gr

[§]Dept. of Informatics, UoWM, Kastoria, Greece

Abstract—With the rise of large language models (LLMs), network management will require significantly less human intervention. This demo shows service deployment from a user request using simple natural language. We leverage LLM to decompose and translate the user request into TM Forum Intent representation. This intent is a blueprint for generating Kubernetes deployment manifest files, ultimately deploying the service to the designated location. This approach significantly reduces manual configuration and streamlines service deployment.

Index Terms—intent-driven deployment, cloud-computing, large language models, management and orchestration, autonomous networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The telecom industry is undergoing a significant transformation driven by the need for ever-increasing network flexibility and automation. Intent-Based Network Management (IBNM) has become a key technology to realize this vision. It simplifies network orchestration and management with Zero-Touch principles and removes the need for manual intervention. This approach helps to develop Intelligent Autonomous Networks capable of self-configuration, optimization, and healing.

The emergence of large language models (LLMs) has further accelerated the progress towards IANs. While LLMs are not yet commonplace in telecom industries, they hold great potential to revolutionize network management. This work investigates how LLMs can translate human intent directly into network configurations. Specifically, we leverage LLMs to translate user requests in natural language into a detailed, well-defined TM Intent representation. LLM-generated Intents bridge human intention and the underlying network infrastructure, enabling autonomous deployment and live migration of network services.

II. RELATED WORK

Several studies have explored the concept of intent-driven management (IDN). The 3GPP TSG Service and System Aspects has proposed intent-driven management services for

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mobile networks [1]. This work investigates the use of TM Forum’s (TMF) API 921 to facilitate communication between communication service consumers and providers. This API emerged from the TMF Intent-Driven Autonomous Networks project, which defined intents’ structure and extension model based on the TMF Intent Ontology [2]. This work proposes an architecture for orchestrating enterprise 5G services, considering user requests expressed as business intents, even without telecommunications expertise. Other works, [3]–[5], proposed IDN solutions to automate the deployment of network slices and manage resources.

The advent of NFV in 5G introduced a paradigm shift for 3GPP systems. This concept has further evolved towards the adoption of cloud-native network functions. Cloud continuum is a frequently considered use case within cloud-native networking. In [2], the authors proposed an intent-based orchestrator for service relocation, demonstrating the potential of intents for orchestrating cloud-native systems. This approach aligns with the growing interest in enterprises ordering 5G services using business intents. IDN is gaining traction as a promising approach for automating and simplifying network operations beyond 5G networks.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

This demo shows an automated service deployment process powered by an LLM, OpenAI’s GPT 3.5 Turbo. A user submits a request using plain natural language describing the desired service. The LLM then analyses the request and generates a standardized TMF-based intent representation. This intent essentially translates the user’s desired request into a machine-readable description. Finally, the system automatically generates detailed deployment instructions using the TMF-based intent. These instructions are then used to create and generate Kubernetes (K8S) Manifest files for the specified service, deploying them to the desired location within the K8S cluster.

IV. DEMONSTRATION

This demo, illustrated in Figure 1, requires internet access for interaction with GPT 3.5 Turbo API. The demo allows the

Fig. 1: Experiment setup: the green box indicates actions performed by the user in the WebUI to deploy the service(s).

user to interact with the WebUI, where it can request/deploy a service using plain natural language, specifically live video streaming and Object Detection(OD) using YoloV8 [6]. The YoloV8 container will be hosted in our cluster. The cluster contains two nodes with different computing capabilities, influencing the latency at which the OD is performed. The cluster distribution is K3S [7]. The steps of the demo are the following:

- 1) The user requests a service using plain natural language
- 2) The LLM will process the request and convert it into a TMF-based intent representation in TTL format.
- 3) Based on the generated intent, the K8s manifest file is generated in YAML format. This file provides detailed deployment instructions for the service.
- 4) The service deployment occurs based on the K8s manifest generated from the intent.
- 5) Service reconfiguration can be requested to live migrate the service to a different location within the network.

Figure 2 shows the live demo in action. On the laptop screen, a user request submitted through the custom WebUI triggers deploying a live video streaming service with OD using YoloV8. The monitor presents the live stream and information about the service deployment in the K8S cluster.

Fig. 2: Live demo

V. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a solution for cloud-native service deployment based on a natural language user request. We present how an LLM translates the request into a TM Forum intent representation, which creates a well-defined K8s deployment file. Our work validates using simple natural language requests for Intent-Driven Deployment using LLM while adhering to enterprise industry standards. We also validate this solution for the live migration of the cloud-native service.

REFERENCES

[1] 3GPP, "Study on enhanced intent driven management services for mobile networks," TR 28.912, 3rd Generation Partnership Project, jul 2023.

[2] B. Orlandi and et al., "From a business intent to a network deployment with user-friendly interfaces and natural language processing," in *2024 27th Conference on Innovation in Clouds, Internet and Networks (ICIN)*, pp. 91–93, March 2024.

[3] J. Zhang and et al., "Intent-driven closed-loop control and management framework for 6g open ran," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2023.

[4] M. Xie and et al., "Intent-driven management for multi-vertical end-to-end network slicing services," in *2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, pp. 1285–1291, 2022.

[5] J. Fonseca and et al., "6g brains topology-aware industry-grade network slice management and orchestration," in *2023 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, pp. 418–423, 2023.

[6] G. Jocher and et al., "Ultralytics YOLO," jan 2023.

[7] "K3s - lightweight kubernetes." <https://k3s.io>.